

APPLICATION OF DUAL EDUCATION IN PRACTICE**Fayziyeva Markhabo Ibragimovna**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8144232>*Qabul qilindi: 13.07.2023**Crossref DOI: 10.24412/cl-37059-2023-07-30-33**UDK: 378.22*

Abstract: In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 08.10.2019 PF5847 on the approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030: modernize higher education, modernize higher education, the social sphere and the economy based on advanced educational technologies. This article discusses the use of dual education in practice.

Key words: dual education, practice, application, system, modernization, dualism.

INTRODUCTION.

Turning science into the main driver of the economy as the main condition for the implementation of these tasks and training competitive specialists based on market requirements are among the urgent tasks of the day. This is the goal behind the idea of the leader of our country to develop the education system on the basis of public-private partnership. The principle of cooperation in education is one of the first in the higher education system of our country was put into practice by the industrial institute. In this regard, as a close partner, on "Targeted training of specialists, mutual cooperation in the fields of educational, scientific and marketing" contracts are formed and the theory acquired on this basis serves to apply knowledge in practice. In this way, a solid foundation for partnership-based cooperation of the parties is created.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY.

If we talk about dualism, dualism (lat. dualis - two sides) is a doctrine that advocates the coexistence of irreconcilable states, principles, ways of thinking, worldviews, aspirations, and epistemological principles. Dualism is a form of pluralism. The term dualism was introduced by the German philosopher H. Wolff

(1679-1754). Dualism represents the following pair of concepts: the world of ideas and the world of reality. Dualism is philosophical, religious, anthropological, can be manifested in ethical forms. In ancient times, religious-ethical dualism is found in the Avesta. Dualism is seen in the philosophy that there are two independent things - spirit and matter. This is especially evident in the views of R. Descartes and I. Kant.

In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", as well as in order to create wide opportunities to support young people's interest in acquiring professions and specialties, dual education will be organized in the professional education system from the 2021/2022 academic year. Article 17 of the Law on Education provides an opinion on dual education, —Dual education is aimed at acquiring the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities by students, and their theoretical part is carried out on the basis of the educational organization, and the practical part is carried out at the workplace of the learner. Procedure for organization of dual education Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan it is determined by the court. The adoption of the Resolution No. 163 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2021 on "Measures for the organization of dual education in the professional education system" indicates that practical work on the organization of dual education has begun in our Republic.

RESEARCH RESULTS.

Dual education is the basis for the training of specialists within the framework of mutual education, involving the educational infrastructure of students and the employer in the educational process. Understanding dual education as a professional relationship experience, transfer of production skills on performance, general principles of interaction on the subject is inextricably linked. In the process of dual education, the student simultaneously applies the theoretical knowledge acquired in the enterprise or organization, strengthening his skills and qualifications in the field of specialization. In this, students develop the ability to spread theoretical knowledge and concepts aimed at understanding a real, specific production process. Science the principle of determining practical activity in the process is based on the main goal of knowledge. The dual education process justifies the objectivity of knowledge with practical activity, which is the power of learning, and is a means of verifying its reality. This is reflected in the dialectical relationship between theory and practice.

DISCUSSION

With this cooperation of the educational institution and the enterprise, the social order for the high-quality and quantitative aspect of the higher education system is determined. According to scientists who have studied the system of vocational education based on the methodical principle of opportunity, the main form of dual education is the Institute of Social Partnership. It is given to the employer with a clear distinction of the interests and obligations of each partner. Bilateral training sessions, not only ensures that certain enterprises, which are interested in the results of specialist training, but also in the educational process and the content of its organization, are involved in the educational process. This is determined by the importance of dual education, which allows filling the gap in the training of a specialist and fields of education. Considering the theoretical and methodological, psychological and philosophical foundations taking into account the professional training of specialists in the conditions of dual training.

It is appropriate to focus on four main components:

1. Motivational (achieving success; motivation to study; job satisfaction level, interest in scientific activity through rationalization proposals).
2. Organizational and management component (manifestation of leadership potential; communicative qualities; organizational characteristics).
3. Cognitive (assimilation of knowledge in professional activity; independence in acquiring knowledge).
4. Scientific component (the level of participation in scientific purposes; the direction of practical innovative projects for solving enterprise problems).

CONCLUSION.

Dual education is understood as an innovative form of organizing professional training, which includes the coordinated interaction of educational and production spheres in the training of specialists of a certain level in accordance with the needs of a certain enterprise. In this case, the common goal of the educational institution and production enterprises is the integration of the process of training competent specialists of certain skills with social structural characteristics. The basis of this integration reflects the community of goals, content of values, activities implemented in the conditions of bilateral training.

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